

The Exploration Mass Spectrometer for LUPEX (EMS-L): Simulations of detecting volatiles at the lunar poles. J. D. Cole¹, S. Sheridan¹, P. Smith¹, A. Morse¹, S. Barber¹ and R. Trautner², ¹The Open University, Walton Hall, Milto Keynes, UK, MK7 6AA (james.cole1@open.ac.uk) ²European Space Agency, Keplerlaan 1, 2201 AZ Noordwijk, Netherlands

Introduction: The EMS-L instrument will operate on JAXA’s LUPEX rover, planned to launch in 2026 onboard an ISRO lander. LUPEX, a 350 kg rover, plans to land at the South Pole and target regions close to and inside Permanently Shadowed Regions (PSRs). The EMS-L Ion Trap Mass Spectrometer (ITMS), shown in Figure 1, will have direct line of sight of the LUPEX drill, which is capable of drilling one meter into the lunar surface. EMS-L may be the first instrument package to access sub-surface materials within a PSR. While LCROSS provided indirect measurements of the volatile inventory of a PSR with the H₂O content of Cabeus crater measured at 5.6 ± 2.9 wt. % [1], EMS-L will provide the first in-situ ground-truth assessment of the volatile inventory of polar and PSR regions. In this work, simulations are presented that demonstrate the ability of EMS-L to contribute significant scientific output over the course of the mission lifetime.

Figure 1: The EMS-L ITMS. The ITMS is present alongside the calibration unit.

Methodology: The Limit of Detection (LoD) is a key characteristic of a ITMS and is dictated by the background pressure achievable inside the instrument cavity. Any volatiles from the lunar surface entering the cavity must be at a pressure above the LoD to be detectable. The PITMS instrument, a precursor to EMS-L, was capable of measuring volatiles in test campaigns at pressures in the order of 10^{-9} mbar [2]. A model has been created that simulates the pressure that is possible inside the ITMS cavity held 30 cm from a pile of volatile rich tailings that has just been exposed onto the lunar surface by the LUPEX drill. A 3D model of a pyramid of cells was created with each cell containing lunar regolith, water ice and methane ice. The physical properties for

each cell was based on the concentration of water and methane in each cell. The quantity of volatiles being released was assessed by calculating the sublimation rate over time in a 3D pyramid made up of cells. The model used the heat equation to assess how the heat from two sunlit faces and the lunar surface temperature changed the temperature of the cells of the tailings. The initial temperature of the tailings, the temperature of the surface and the initial concentration of water in the tailings was altered. Table 1 shows the variables used in the model. Figure 2 shows the initial setup of the 3D pyramid. The pressure inside the ITMS was assessed by assuming the volatiles travel away from the pyramid in a spherical shell towards the ITMS. A fraction of the released volatiles are able to enter the ITMS cavity through the aperture that causes an increase in the pressure.

Table 1: Variables used in the model.

Variable	Value
Time of Exposure	1000 s
Initial Tailings Temperature	50-200 K
Surface Temperature	50 – 400 K
Water Ice Concentration	1 – 10 wt. %
Methane Ice Concentration	0.1 – 3 wt. %

Figure 2: Setup of the tailings pyramid.

Results: Figure 3 shows the peak pressure in the ITMS for different combination of volatile concentrations and initial temperatures. A white line is shown to indicate the LoD of the ITMS at 10^{-9} mbar. Pressures above this show where significant events would be seen. All concentrations of volatiles that were used allow pressures $>10^{-9}$ mbar. Figure 3 shows how the temperature of both the tailings and the surface directly impact the peak pressure seen in

the ITMS. Future work will concentrate on establishing how these results can be correlated to a concept of operations. The temperature patterns can be used to target specific areas on the lunar surface.

Figure 3: Pressure inside the ITMS due to volatiles released from the tailings in 1000 seconds.

Conclusions: The model shows that EMS-L has the capability to detect and analyse volatiles on the lunar surface. By doing so, EMS-L will contribute to analysing the volatile inventory of the lunar poles with the potential of contributing the first direct measurements of volatiles in these areas. The results have the potential to inform future lunar missions where to target for resource prospecting and extraction. Scientifically, such results will make significant contributions to understanding the volatile inventory of the solar system.

References: [1] Colaprete A. et al. (2010) *Science*, 330, 6003, 463-468 [2] Cohen B. A. et al. (2024) *The Planetary Science Journal*, 5:212